

**AN INVESTIGATION OF THE RELATIONSHIP
BETWEEN ATTITUDE TOWARDS TURKISH LANGUAGE
AND LITERATURE LESSON AND SCHOOL BURNOUT
USING STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODEL**

Fatih Veyisⁱ

Asst. Prof. Dr.,
Atatürk University,
Erzurum, Turkey

Abstract:

In this study, the predictive effect of school burnout in secondary education students on the attitude towards the Turkish language and literature lesson was investigated. School burnout is considered as one of the important problems that are thought to negatively affect student life in recent years. The study group of the research consists of 530 students studying in secondary education in a city center. The study group was determined by the appropriate sampling method with reference to the 99% confidence interval. In the research, the school burnout scale and attitude scale towards the Turkish language and literature lesson were used to collect data. Correlation analysis and structural equation modeling techniques were used for data analysis. Findings obtained from the study revealed that there was a negative and significant relationship between school burnout and attitude towards Turkish language and literature lesson, and school burnout directly predicted the attitude towards Turkish language and literature lesson. It was concluded from the findings obtained that school burnout is an important risk source in terms of attitude towards Turkish language and literature lesson among secondary education students.

Keywords: school burnout, attitude towards Turkish language and literature lesson, structural equation model

1. Introduction

The secondary education period covers a number of processes that affect students in many ways as both the adolescence period is intensely experienced and the processes of preparing for life, adulthood and profession should be successfully fulfilled. In this process, students display behaviors that can sometimes be described as unsuccessful in

ⁱ Correspondence: email fatih.veyis@atauni.edu.tr

the face of the roles and responsibilities they must fulfill, and these behaviors can reveal undesirable results that may cause students to be affected psychologically, socially and physically. The state of the individual's full health is defined by the World Health Organization (1998) as a state of full well-being in physical, social and spiritual terms. As can be understood from this definition, health is not only seen as a state of physical well-being but is evaluated as a whole with its social and psychological dimensions. Secondary education students are likely to face situations that may cause them to be negatively affected and experience some adjustment problems, given the responsibilities they have to fulfill and the difficulties they have to overcome for four years.

Secondary education students may experience school burnout, a problem that has been addressed as a common problem in recent years among the possible negativities experienced by personal and social processes in addition to these academic processes. Although burnout is predominantly a concept considered for professional life, views such as constantly giving students excessive duties and responsibilities in educational activities, excessive expectation on students to fulfill these duties and responsibilities and considering studentship as a business in recent years have gained importance, and burnout started to be examined in terms of educational activities (Schaufeli et al. 2002; Salmela-Aro, Kiuru, Leskinen and Nurmi, 2009; Salmelo-Aro, Savolainen & Holopainen, 2008; Seçer et al., 2013; Seçer & Gençdoğan, 2012). Moving from the idea that students' success and attitudes towards the Turkish language and literature lesson may also be affected by different psychological variables, and burnout can predict attitudes towards the lesson, the idea of to what level burnout, which has been seen as an important risk in recent years, predicts Turkish language and literature lesson is the starting point of this research.

School burnout can be defined as the situation where students feel inadequate against the demands of the school, thereby decreasing their attachment by developing a negative attitude towards the school (Salmela-Aro et al., 2009; Fredricks, Blumenfeld and Paris, 2004; Schaufeli, Salanova, Gonzales-Roma and Bakker, 2002).

The concept of school burnout is defined by symptoms and outcomes such as students' negative attitude towards lessons and school as a result of academic stress caused by high success expectations, decreased academic motivation and negative self-perception (Salmela-Aro, Kiuru, Leskinen and Nurmi, 2009). The high expectation of the family and social environment, which can be considered as external factors that cause school burnout, causes the student to experience more academic stress and feel inadequate when he/she cannot perform the expected performance. As a result, the belief of the student who feels inadequate is broken and gives up studying (Aypay and Eryilmaz, 2011).

Similar to the model established by Maslach and Jackson (1981) on burnout, Parker and Salmela-Aro (2011) tried to explain school burnout with a 3-dimensional model, which was neglecting, emotional exhaustion and inadequacy that negatively affect educational activities. Parker and Salmela-Aro (2011) concluded that emotional exhaustion is the first component of school burnout and that the person becomes

insensitive as a result of emotional exhaustion. As a result of the desensitization that occurs in the person, the individual develops dysfunctional coping strategies and thus, the person develops the feeling that he is not competent.

When the research conducted in recent years are examined, it is concluded that school burnout is associated with many psychosocial variables. Academic success (McCarthy, Pretty and Catano, 1990; Balkis, Duru, Invention and Duru, 2011), academic motivation (Meier & Schmeck, 1985; Ramist, 1981), academic stress (Salmela-Aro, Parker, 2011; Guthrie et al., 1998; Dahlin, Joneborg and Runeson 2007; Humphris et al., 2002), self-esteem, depressive symptom, general stress state (Salmela-Aro, Parker, 2011), anxiety (Slivar 2001; Salmela-Aro, Parker 2011), tendency to perfectionism (Gotwals, 2011; Shu-Shen, 2012), inability to empathize (Mazurkiewicz, Korenstein & Fallar, 2012; Dyrbye, Eacker, Anne, Harper, William, 2012), absenteeism and school dropout (Meier & Schmeck, 1985 Variables such as Ramist, 1981) were found to be important predictors of school burnout.

Among the concepts that have a close relationship with school burnout and have an impact on it, attitudes towards the lesson can also be shown. Attitude is defined as "*the path taken, manner*" (TDK, 2011: 2393). The concept of attitude generally refers to the reaction tendency related to any phenomenon or object around the individual (İnceoğlu, 2010). Attitude can be defined as the value that people place on objects or thoughts (Çelik, 2015: 276). In educational researches, it is revealed that the attitudes of the individuals towards the material to be learned, the teacher and the subject area he/she studies affect their school success (Ağgön & Yazıcı, 2010). Since education is an important tool in changing attitudes, the fact that teachers know what student attitudes are towards their own lessons and other social life situations and how to measure them can be an important factor in increasing the quality of education (Inan, 2014: 383). Students have many roles and responsibilities that they must fulfill academically starting from primary school years. Among these, responsibilities such as success in centralized exams, preparation for the profession and higher education institutions, and meeting the expectations of the family are expected. There are research results showing that it is inevitable for students to experience depression in case they fail to meet these roles and responsibilities they must fulfill (Harrington & Clark, 1998; Ryff & Singer, 2008). Considering the negativities and insignificance and failure feelings occur as a result of emotional burnout and depersonalization of school burnout the students will experience in this process, it is evaluated that there is a close relationship between the attitude towards the Turkish language and literature lesson and school burnout. In other words, in terms of school burnout results, it can be considered as an important risk source that may affect students' attitudes towards the Turkish language and literature lesson. Therefore, in this research process, the relationship between burnout and attitude towards the Turkish language and literature lesson was aimed to be addressed and answers to the two questions given below were sought.

Research question 1: Is there a significant relationship between secondary education the limitations in the research process students' burnout and their attitudes towards the Turkish language and literature lesson?

Research question 2: Does school burnout in secondary education students significantly predict the attitude towards Turkish language and literature lesson?

2. Method

2.1 Research Model

This research aims to examine the predictive relationships between school burnout and attitude towards the Turkish language and literature lesson in accordance with the correlational survey model. The correlational survey model is defined as the research method that allows in-depth analysis in determining the relationships between variables (Karakaya, 2011). The correlational survey process consists of defining the problem status, determining the research design and sampling processes, collecting and analyzing the data and discussing the results obtained. In this context, in the first stage, the relevant literature has been reviewed in relation to the research process, and the problem status has been addressed. In the second stage, a sample which can represent the research population was formed in order to achieve the specified goal. For this purpose, the convenience sampling method was used to determine the sample units. In the third stage, the validity and reliability levels of the scales were reviewed, and data were collected to ensure that data collection tools provide validity and reliability. At the last stage, Correlation Analysis and Implicit Variables and Structural Equation Model were used to find answers to the questions sought in the research process. Findings from these analyses in the last stage have been interpreted and discussed in the context of the relevant literature.

2.2 Study Group

The study group of the research consists of 530 students studying at secondary education institutions in a city center. When calculating the sample size of the research, 99% confidence interval was taken as reference. The sampling selection method of the research is the convenience sampling method. Appropriate sampling is a sampling type that is used in situations that make it impossible to reach all of the population, and the researcher can easily access the sampling elements (Bayram, 2009). Although it is seen as a disadvantage in the research process since the use of convenience sampling method as a sampling method in the research process is not a probabilistic method, all school types in the population were tried to be reached and samples were taken from all of them in order to eliminate this disadvantage. In this context, sampling units were tried to be taken to represent all of the secondary education institutions such as the Anatolian high schools, Science-Social Sciences high schools, Vocational and Technical High Schools etc. that are included in the research population. The age average of the participants in the study group is 17.35 and 273 of the participants are male and 257 are female.

2.3 Data Collection Tools

Two different measurement tools and a personal information protocol were used in the data collection process.

A. The School Burnout Inventory was developed by Salmela-Aro et al (2009) to determine the levels of students' burnout and is a self-reporting scale in Likert type, whose psychometric properties were adapted to Turkish culture by Seer et al. (2013). The scale consists of three sub-dimensions as indifference, emotional burnout and a low sense of personal success and ten items in total. Expert opinion was consulted to ensure language validity to the adaptation process of the scale. Confirmatory factor analysis was done in order to determine the construct validity of the scale, and it was determined that the three-factor structure of the scale fit well in Turkish culture (RMSEA = .042, RMR = .013, GFI = .92, AGFI = .90, CFI = .96, NFI = .90,, RFI = .92, IFI = .97). The internal consistency coefficient of the scale was found to be .75 and two half reliability was .72.

In this research process, CFA analysis was done to determine the reliability and validity values of the scale, and it was found as RMSEA = .061, CFI = .97, SRMR: .58, GFI = .92. The reliability value of the scale was found as .78. These findings obtained during the research were evaluated as the scale is a valid and reliable measurement tool.

B. Attitude Scale towards Turkish Language and Literature Lesson; is a Likert-type measurement tool developed by Veyis (2015) and consisting of 27 items and four sub-dimensions. The sub-dimensions of the scale are the interest in the Turkish literature lesson, considering the Turkish literature lesson as important, avoiding the Turkish literature lesson and knowledge dimensions, respectively. As a result of the EFA in the development process of the scale, it was concluded that it explained 58.39% of the total variance. The internal consistency coefficient of the scale was .95 and the split-half reliability coefficient was .79. In this research process, the validity and reliability values of the scale were re-examined and found as RMSEA = .078, CFI = .97, SRMR: .075, GFI = .97. The reliability coefficient of the scale was found to be .95. As a result, these findings were evaluated as the scale is a valid and reliable measurement tool.

2.4 Data Analysis

For the data collected in the research process, first of all, lost data analysis was made and it was decided to remove the scales containing the missing data above 2% from the data set. After the extracted data, the study was carried out with 530 people. Normality and homogeneity analyses were carried out to determine whether the data collected in the research process met the parametric conditions. To determine extreme values before normality tests, kurtosis and skewness values and extreme values were determined by doing the Mahalanobis test. In this context, it was decided to extract from the data set since 23 of the scales had serious gaps and the data belonging to 17 people contained extreme values that would disturb normality. In this sense, the Levene homogeneity test, histogram and Kolmogorov-Smirnov test were performed. After determining that the data set provides parametric conditions, Correlation Analysis and Implicit Variables and Structural Equation Model were used. REMSEA, RMR, SRMR, AGFI, GFI, RFI, IFI, NFI

and CFI, which are referenced in the structural equation model, were used (Marcoulides and Schumacher, 2001). SPSS 22.00 software and LISREL 9.2 software were used for data analysis.

3. Findings

In this section, the findings obtained in the research process are explained below in relation to the questions that are answered within the scope of the research.

3.1 Examining the Relationship Between School Burnout and Turkish Language and Literature Lesson

Pearson Product-Moment Correlation analysis was used to determine the relationship between school burnout scores and attitude scores towards the Turkish language and literature lesson of secondary education students, and the data obtained are given in Table 1.

Table 1: The Relationship Between School Burnout and Attitude towards Turkish Language and Literature Lesson

		T.L.L.A			
		Interest	Importance	Avoidance	Information
S.B.	Emotional Burnout	-.271**	-.334**	.182**	-.201**
	Indifference	-.208**	-.277**	.091*	-.199**
	Feeling of Low Success	-.305**	-.345**	.176**	-.259**

* p <.05, ** p <.01 - S.B. = School Burnout, T.L.L.A.= Turkish Literature Lesson Attitude

When Table 1 is analyzed, it is seen that there is a negative and significant relationship between emotional burnout, indifference, and feeling of low individual success sub-dimensions of school burnout and interest, importance and knowledge subdimensions of the attitude towards TLLA, but positive and significant relationships with avoidance sub-dimension. As a result of these findings, it can be said that the increase in school burnout has a negative effect on students' attitudes towards the Turkish language and literature lesson.

After determining the significant relationship between school burnout and TLLA, latent variables and structural equation model were used to determine the predictive effect of school burnout on TLLA. For this purpose, the confirmatory measurement model was first tested to determine the model fit between school burnout and TLLA, and the fit index values obtained are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Fit Indices of Confirmatory Measurement Model

X ²	sd	X ² /Sd	NFI	CFI	IFI	RFI	GFI	SRM	RMR	RMSEA
25.59	11	2.32	.99	.99	.99	.97	.99	.030	.29	.050

When the model fit indices (Table 2) of the confirmatory measurement model are examined, it is seen that the confirmatory measurement model established between TLLA and school burnout fits well and the model fit indexes are at a good level.

In addition, there was a negative and significant relationship between TLLA and school burnout ($r(530) = -.47$). After the established measurement model and model fit indices fit well, the latent variable was determined for school burnout and TLLA, and the analysis was continued with these implicit variables. In this context, the latent variables were used for the school burnout variable (BURN) and attitude towards the Turkish language and literature lesson (TLLA). The BURN latent variable was measured by indifference, emotional burnout, and feeling of low individual success. The TLLA variable was measured by the variables of interest, knowledge, importance and avoidance. Results related to the structural equation model established after the measurement model are given in Figure 1. In addition, multiple model fit indexes related to the structural equation model are given in Table 3.

Figure 1: Structural Equation Model Between School Burnout and TLLA

Table 3: Model goodness of fit indexes related to the structural equation model

χ^2	sd	χ^2 / Sd	AGFI	RFI	CFI	IFI	GFI	NFI	NNFI	RMR	REMSEA
28.82	13	2.21	.96	.97	.99	.99	.99	.98	.98	.030	.051

When the standardized values of the structural equation model given in Figure 1 and the fit index values given in Table 3 are examined, it can be said that the model established between school burnout and TLLA is verified (Marcoulides & Schumacher, 2001; Hu & Bentler, 1999).

3.2 Coefficients of Determination for the Structural Equation Model

The coefficient of determination is used in the structural equation model to show how much the predictor variable explains the variance on the predicted variable. The coefficient of determination among variables is between 0 and 1. The findings regarding the coefficients of explaining the variance of school burnout on TLLA are given in Table 4.

Table 4: Coefficients of Determination for the Structural Equation Model

Fit parameter	Coefficient value
X1: Emotional Burnout	.74
X2: Indifference	.78
X3: Feeling Of Low Success	.74
Y1: Interest	.67
Y2: Importance	.78
Y3: Avoidance	.50
Y4: Knowledge	.53
$\xi_{1:\eta_1}$	-.23

When Table 4 is examined, it is seen that school burnout explains 23% of the variance in TLLA. In addition, when the measurement models are considered, school burnout explains 74% of the variance in emotional burnout, 78% of the variance in the indifference variable and 74% of the variance in feeling of low individual success, the indicator variables of the latent variable. The TLLA latent variable explains 67% of the variance in the interest dimension, 78% of the variance in the importance dimension, 50% of the variance in the avoidance dimension and 53% of the variance in the knowledge dimension, which are the indicator variables. Based on the findings obtained, it was determined that the latent variables explained sufficient variance in the indicator variables defining them, and school burnout negatively and significantly predicted TLLA.

3.3 Findings Regarding Total and Indirect Effects in the Structural Equation Model

The total and indirect effects of school burnout on attitude towards the Turkish language and literature lesson are given in Table 5.

Table 5: Direct and indirect effects on SEM

	Total effect		Indirect effect
	School Burnout	TLLA	School Burnout
Emotional burnout	.69		
Indifference	.75		
Feeling of low individual success	.64		
Interest	.24	.80	.24
Importance	.23	.71	.23
Avoidance	.15	.64	.15
Information	.15	.72	.15

When Table 5 is examined, it can be said that the latent variables created to symbolize school burnout and TLLA directly affect the indicator variables that constitute them, whereas both latent variables indirectly affect the indicator variable of the other latent variable. In other words, while the latent variable of school burnout directly predicts the implicit variable of TLLA, it indirectly affects and predicts the sub-dimensions of this implicit variable, which are indicator variables.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

In this research process, the predictive effect of school burnout levels of secondary education students on attitude scores towards the Turkish language and literature course was examined. In this context, answers to two questions were sought in the research. These are "Is there a significant relationship between school burnout and attitude towards Turkish language and literature lesson, and does school burnout predict secondary education students' attitudes towards Turkish language and literature?"

The fit indices of the established structural equation model showed a perfect fit (Hu and Bentler, 1999). In line with the results obtained from the research, it was concluded that school burnout predicted the attitude towards Turkish language and literature lesson in the dimensions of interest, importance, and knowledge negatively, and in the avoidance dimension positively. When the fit indexes of the model were examined, it was seen that the model had perfect fit values. In the structural equation model, it was concluded that it can perfectly explain the relationships between latent variables (Hu and Bentler, 1999; Marcoulides and Schumacher, 2001).

As a result, it can be said that school burnout is an important risk source for the attitude scores of the students of secondary education level towards the Turkish language and literature lesson. In line with the findings obtained from the research, it can be said that the increase in school burnout in adolescents will have a significant negative effect on attitude towards the Turkish language and literature lesson.

One of the most important indicators of the students' affective characteristics related to the lesson is their attitudes (Gardner & Lambert, 1972; Stern, 1983; Brown, 2001; Karasakal & Saracaloğlu, 2009; Kaya et al., 2009). While positive attitudes make students more successful, negative attitudes can cause failure. Therefore, it is of high importance to know the circumstances affecting the attitude and taking remedial steps in this

direction. In this context, it can be said that school burnout, which has a negative effect on the attitude towards Turkish language and literature lesson in adolescents, may trigger some other negative situations through indirect processes by creating a negative effect on self-perception and self-evaluation of the individual.

When the research on attitude is examined, it is seen that many studies are carried out to determine the attitudes of the students towards the lesson, and various variables that can be effective on attitude are obtained. Accordingly, variables such as gender, class level, school type, teacher's approach to the course and the student, the time spent on the social media, the frequency of reading the book, the educational status of the parents, the socio-economic level of the family, the student's interest in the lesson, etc. can be effective on students' developing positive or negative attitudes towards the lesson. According to the research in the literature, it has been observed that female students have a more positive attitude towards Turkish language and literature lesson compared to male students. The positive attitude of the teacher towards the lesson and the student and the positive feelings of the student towards the teacher are effective in the development of the student's positive attitude towards the Turkish language and literature lesson. It has been determined that students who have improved in the frequency of reading and sparing the time to read books develop a more positive attitude towards Turkish language and literature lesson than students who read less and devote less time to reading. In addition, it is observed that the children with parents with high education level and in a good socio-economical position generally have a positive attitude towards the lessons (Selçuk, 1997; Erdem, 2013; Kılıç, 2018; Ateş, 2008; Bölükbaş, 2010; Karadağ, 2012; Karakuş Aktan, 2013).

It was concluded in the majority of the studies examining the relationship between academic success and attitude towards the lesson that success and attitude have a significant relationship. Selçuk (1997) determined in their research on the freshman that there is a significant and positive relationship between students' attitudes towards English language lesson and their academic achievements in this lesson. Anbarlı and Kırız (2010), on the other hand, concluded in their research on 8th and 11th-grade students for English language lessons that students with high academic achievement also had high attitude points towards the lesson in their study. Yücel and Koç (2011) found a positive and significant relationship between students' mathematics attitude and their mathematics achievement. When the research on Turkish language and Turkish language and literature lessons are analyzed, it is seen that they have similar results with other researches. Ateş (2008) determined that there is a positive relationship between attitude towards Turkish language lesson and reading comprehension, Turkish language academic achievement and general academic achievement. Özdemir (2008) concluded that there is a relationship between 9th grade students' attitudes towards Turkish literature lesson and their academic achievement, and students whose attitudes towards Turkish literature are positive have higher academic success rates. Karakuş Aktan (2013) states that students who develop a positive attitude towards language and expression lesson have higher academic success.

Contrary to the studies indicating that there is a positive and significant relationship between attitude and academic achievement, there are also studies indicating that there is no relationship or negative relationship between these two variables. Kazazoğlu (2013) states in his study that there is a significant relationship between the attitude towards Turkish language lesson and the Turkish language final grade among the sub-dimensions of the attitude, but no relationship can be found on the total scores. Peker and Mirasyedioğlu (2003), on the other hand, state that although students generally develop positive attitudes towards mathematics, the success rate is low. Kılıç (2018) found that there is no significant relationship between students' general academic achievement scores and attitudes regarding the Turkish language and literature lesson. When the relevant literature related to attitude is analyzed and considering that the number of studies reaching the conclusion that the attitude has a positive effect on academic achievement is higher, it can be argued that the studies that reach different results differ due to sample, relevant lesson and environmental factors.

Among the other variables that attitude is effective, as stated in Fidan and Eren's (2017) studies, motivation can also be counted. Accordingly, there is a positive relationship between students having a high level of intrinsic motivation and developing a positive attitude towards the Turkish language lesson. Karadağ (2012) states that students who develop negative attitudes have problems in interest in the lesson and that the lesson is ineffective at improving the cognitive development of the students. In the study conducted by Sevim and Varışoğlu (2012), it was stated that attitude towards teaching profession affects professional success.

As can be seen, the student's attitude towards the lesson affects the student's academic achievement, intrinsic motivation, and cognitive development and is also influenced by many variables. School burnout is one of these variables.

School burnout is a risk factor for students in many ways. Koçak (2016) states that school burnout constitutes an important risk factor for depression in students. According to the study of Akpınar (2016), school burnout plays an intermediary role between academic stress and subjective well-being, and the increase in school burnout negatively affects subjective well-being in adolescents. Demir (2015) states that students with high academic success experience more school burnout, whereas students with high school burnout have higher exam anxiety. Seçer (2015) states that school burnout negatively affects academic motivation and therefore, school burnout poses a significant risk for academic motivation.

Özdemir (2015) counts school attachment among the variables that negatively affect school burnout but states that increasing the time students spare to do homework and low academic motivation increase school burnout. In addition, student-teacher relationships, self-regulation, family participation in school and positive increase in peer relationships are among the factors that decrease school burnout in high school students (Özhan, 2019).

Studies that examine the effect of school burnout on students' attitudes towards school and the lesson seem to have reached similar results. Kurt (2019) found that there

is a negative, strong and significant relationship between high school students' school burnout and their attitude towards mathematics lesson. Koç (2019) found that the increase in attitude scores towards school in adolescents and values such as responsibility, friendship, peacefulness, respect, honesty, and tolerance have an effect on reducing school burnout.

When the research on school burnout and attitude are analyzed, it is seen that the results are similar to the school burnout reached as a result of this research, which predicted negatively the attitude towards Turkish language and literature lesson in terms of interest, importance, and knowledge, but positively in avoidance.

Lastly, the limitations of the research in the interpretation of the findings obtained in the research process should also be evaluated. The first limitation of the research is that the study group consists of students at the secondary education level. Therefore, since the results obtained can only be generalized on this group, it is thought that it would be beneficial to carry out similar research at other age and education levels. The second limitation can be that the research involves a cross-sectional research process. In order to overcome this limitation, it is evaluated that longitudinal studies and planning of research patterns by adding new variables will contribute to the scientific accumulation and to create awareness in this direction.

The recommendations that can be made based on the research findings are as follows:

- 1) Considering the effect of school burnout on students' attitudes towards Turkish language and literature lesson, school burnout should be identified in studies to determine and improve students' attitudes towards this lesson, and necessary precautions should be taken in this regard.
- 2) Considering the negative effects of school burnout on students, the factors that cause school burnout in students should be investigated in a comprehensive and holistic way.
- 3) In addition to school burnout, other variables that may have positive and negative effects should be determined on the attitudes of students towards Turkish language and literature lesson, and plans and programs should be developed in a way to improve students' attitudes towards this lesson.
- 4) Teachers and parents should be informed about school burnout, and they should work in cooperation with the school guidance service.

References

- Akpınar M, 2016. Okul tükenmişliği ile akademik stres ve öznel iyi oluş arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesi. Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Atatürk Üniversitesi.
- Anbarlı Kırkız Y, 2010. Öğrencilerin İngilizce dersine ait tutumları ile akademik başarıları arasındaki ilişki. Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Trakya Üniversitesi.

- Ateş M, 2008. İlköğretim ikinci kademe öğrencilerinin okuduğunu anlama düzeyleri ile Türkçe dersine karşı tutumları ve akademik başarıları arasındaki ilişki. Doktora Tezi, Selçuk Üniveristesi.
- Aypay A, Eryılmaz A, 2011. Lise Öğrencilerinin Derse Katılmaya Motive Olmaları ile Okul Tükenmişliği Arasındaki İlişkinin İncelenmesi. Mehmet Akif Ersoy Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi 21: 26-44.
- Bölükbaş F, 2010. İlköğretim Öğrencilerinin Türkçe Dersine Yönelik Tutumlarının Başarı-Cinsiyet-Ailenin Eğitim Düzeyi Bağlamında Değerlendirilmesi. Turkish Studies 5(3): 905-918.
- Brown H.D, 2001. Teaching by Principles: An Interactive Approach to Language Pedagogy, Second Edition, San Francisco Public University.
- Buluş M, Duru E, Balkıs M, Duru S, 2011. Öğrenme Stratejileri ve Bireysel Özelliklerin Akademik Başarıyı Öngörmedeki Rolü. Eğitim ve Bilim Dergisi 36(161): 186-198.
- Çelik T, 2015. Öğrencilerin e-Kitap Okuma Alışkanlıklarının Değerlendirilmesi. Turkish Studies International Periodical for the Languages, Literature and History of Turkish or Turkic 10(3): 271-284.
- Dahlin M, Joneborg N, Runeson B, 2007. Performance-Based Self-Esteem and Burnout in a Cross-Sectional Study of Medical Students. Medical Teacher 29: 43-48.
- Demir M, 2015. Okul tükenmişliğinin yordanmasında sınav kaygısı ve akademik başarının etkisi. Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Atatürk Üniversitesi.
- Dyrbye L.N, Eacker A.M, Harper W, 2012. Distress and Empathy do not Drive Changes in Specialty Preference among US Medical Students. Medical Teacher 34(2): 116-122.
- Erdem C, 2013. Ortaöğretim Öğrencilerinin Türk Edebiyatı Dersine Yönelik Tutumları Üzerine Bir Değerlendirme. Adıyaman Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi Türkçenin Eğitimi Öğretimi Özel Sayısı 6(11): 381-414.
- Fidan M, Eren A, 2017. Ortaokul Öğrencilerinin Türkçe Dersine Yönelik Tutum Görünümleri ile Eğitime İlişkin Motivasyonları Arasındaki İlişkiler. Hacettepe Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi 32(2): 480-493.
- Fredricks J,A, Blumenfeld P.C, Paris A.H, 2004. School Engagement: Potential of the Concept, State of the Evidence. Review of Educational Research 74: 59-109.
- Gardner R.C, Lambert W.E, 1972. Attitudes and Motivation in Second Language Learning. Newbury House: Rowley, Massachusetts.
- Gotwals J.K, 2011. Perfectionism and Burnout within Intercollegiate Sport: A Person-Oriented Approach. The Sport Psychologist 25: 489-510.
- Guthri E, Black D, Bagalkote H, Shaw C, Campbell M, Creed F, 1998. Psychological stress and Burnout Inmedicalstudents: A Five-Year Prospective Longitudinal Study. Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine 91: 237-243.
- Harrington R, Clark A, 1998. Prevention and Early Intervention for Depression in Adolescence and Early Adult Life. Eur Arch Psychiatry Clin Neurosci 248:32-45.

- Hu L.T, Bentler, P.M, 1999. Cutoff Criteria for Fit Indexes in Covariance Structural Analysis: Conventional Criteria Versus New Alternatives. *Structural Equation Modeling* 6(1): 55-65.
- Humphris G, Blinkhorn A, Freeman R, Gorter R, Reddick G, 2002. Psychological Stress in Under Graduate Dental Students: Baseline Results from Seven European Dental Schools. *European Journal of Dental Education* 6: 22-29.
- İnceođlu M, 2010. Tutum Algı İletişim. İstanbul: Beykent Üniversitesi Yayınları.
- Jackson L.T, Van de Vijver F.J, Fouché R, 2014. Psychological Strengths and Subjective Well-Being in South African White Students. *Journal of Psychology in Africa* 24(4): 299-307.
- Karadađ B.A, 2012. Ortaöğretim öğrencileri ve öğretmenlerinin Türk edebiyatı dersine yönelik tutumlarının değerlendirilmesi: Taşköprü örneđi. Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Gazi Üniversitesi.
- Karakuş Aktan E.N, 2013. Öğrencilerin dil ve anlatım dersine yönelik tutumlarının akademik başarılarıyla ilişkisi (Çankaya ilçesi örneđi). Yüksek Lisans Tezi. Gazi Üniveristesi.
- Karasakal N, Saracalođlu A.S, 2009. Sınıf Öğretmeni Adaylarının Türkçe Derslerine Yönelik Tutumları, Akademik Benlik Tasarımları ile Başarıları Arasındaki İlişki. *Yüzüncü Yıl Üniversitesi, Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi* VI(I): 343-362.
- Kaya A.İ, Arslantaş H.İ, Şimşek N, 2009. İlköğretim Öğrencilerinin Türkçe Tutumlarının Deđerlendirilmesi. *Elektronik Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi* 30: 367-387.
- Kazazođlu S, 2013. Türkçe ve İngilizce Derslerine Yönelik Tutumun Akademik Başarıya Etkisi. *Eđitim ve Bilim*, 38(170): 294-307.
- Kılıç D, 2018. 11. sınıf öğrencilerinin Türk edebiyatı dersine ilişkin tutumları üzerine inceleme. Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Yıldız Teknik Üniversitesi.
- Koç A, 2019. Ergenlerin sahip oldukları deđerler ile okula yönelik tutumları ve okul tükenmişlik düzeyleri arasındaki yordayıcı ilişkiler. Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Necmettin Erbakan Üniversitesi.
- Koçak L, 2016. Lise öğrencilerinde okul tükenmişliđi ile depresif belirtiler arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesi. Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Atatürk Üniversitesi.
- Kurt H, 2019. Lise öğrencilerinin okul tükenmişliđi ile matematik dersine yönelik tutumları arasındaki ilişki. Yüksek Lisans Tezi. Gaziantep Üniversitesi.
- Marcoulides G, Schumacher R, 2001. New developments and techniques in structural equation modeling. London: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Publishers.
- Maslach C, Jackson S.E, 1981. The Measurement of Experienced Burnout. *Journal of Occupational Behavior* 2: 99-113.
- Mazurkiewicz R, Korenstein D, Fallar R, 2012. The Prevalence and Correlations of Medical Student Burnout in the Pre-Clinical Years: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Psychology Health & Medicine* 17(2): 188-195.
- McCarthy M.E, Pretty G.M, Catano V, 1990. Psychological Sense of Community and Student Burnout. *Journal of College Student Development* 31: 211-216.

- Meier S.F, Schmeck R.R, 1985. The Burned-Out College Student: A Descriptive Profile. *Journal of College Student Personal* 26: 63–69.
- Özdemir B, 2008. 9. Sınıf öğrencilerinin Türk edebiyatı dersine yönelik tutumlarının Türk edebiyatı dersi akademik başarısına etkisi(Kütahya örneği). Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Gazi Üniversitesi.
- Özdemir Y, 2015. Ortaokul Öğrencilerinde Okul Tükenmişliği: Ödev, Okula Bağlılık ve Akademik Motivasyonun Rolü. *Eğitim Bilimleri Dergisi* 6(1): 27-35.
- Özhan M.B, 2019. Lise öğrencilerinde okul tükenmişliğinin akademik başarı ve iyi oluşa etkisinin bütüncül olarak incelenmesi. Doktora Tezi. Gazi Üniversitesi.
- Peker M, Mirasyedioğlu Ş, 2003. Lise 2. Sınıf Öğrencilerinin Matematik Dersine Yönelik Tutumları ve Başarıları Arasındaki İlişki. *Pamukkale Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi* 2(14): 157-166.
- Ramist L, 1981. College Student Attrition and Retention. *Findings (ETS)* 6: 1–4.
- Ryff C.D, Singer B.H, 2008. Know Thyself and Become What You Are: A Eudaimonic Approach to Psychological Well-Being. *Journal of Happiness Studies* 9(1): 13-39.
- Salmela-Aro K, Kiuru N, Leskinen I.E, Nurmi E, 2009. School-Burnout Inventory: Reliability and Validity. *European Journal of Psychological Assessment* 25(1): 48–57.
- Salmela-Aro K, Kiuru N, Pietikäinen M, Jokela J, 2008. Does School Matter? The Role of School Context in Adolescents' School-Related Burnout. *European Psychologist* 13(1): 12-23.
- Salmela-Aro K, Parker P.D, 2011. Developmental Processes in School Burnout: A Comparison of Major Developmental Models. *Learning and Individual Differences* 21: 244-248.
- Schaufeli W.B, Martinez M.I, Pinto A.M, Salanova M, Bakker A.B, 2002. Burnout and Engagement in University Students - A Cross National Study. *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology* 33(5): 464- 481.
- Seçer İ, 2015. Okul Tükenmişliği ile Akademik Güdülenme Arasındaki İlişkinin Yapısal Eşitlik Modeli ile İncelenmesi. *Journal of Research in Education and Teaching* 4(1): 424-433.
- Seçer İ, Gençdoğan B, 2012. Ortaöğretim Öğrencilerinde Okul Tükenmişliğinin Çeşitli Değişkenler Açısından İncelenmesi. *Turkish Journal of Education* 1(2): 1-13.
- Seçer İ, Halmatov S, Veyis F, Ateş B, 2013. Okul Tükenmişlik Ölçeğinin Türk Kültürüne Uyarlanması: Güvenirlilik ve Geçerlik Çalışması. *Turkish Journal of Education* 2(2): 16-27.
- Selçuk E, 1997. İngilizce dersine karşı tutum ile bu dersteki akademik başarı arasındaki ilişki. Yüksek Lisans Tezi. Abant İzzet Baysal Üniversitesi.
- Sevim, O, Varışoğlu, B. (2012). Duygusal Semantik Farklılığa Göre Atatürk Üniversitesindeki Türkçe Öğretmeni Adaylarının Öğretmenlik Mesleğine Yükledikleri Değerler. *Uluslararası Türkçe Edebiyat Kültür Eğitim Dergisi* 1(2): 27-37.

- Shu S.S, 2012. An Examination of Academic Burnout versus Work Engagement among Taiwanese Adolescents. *Journal of Educational Research* 105(4): 286-298.
- Slivar B, 2001. The Syndrome of Burnout, Self-Image, and Anxiety with Grammar School Students. *Horizons of Psychology* 10(2): 21-32.
- Stern H.H, 1983. *Fundamental concepts of language teaching*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- TDK, 2011. *Türkçe Sözlük*, Ankara: Türk Dil Kurumu Yayınları.
- World Health Organization (WHO), 1998. *Wellbeing measures in primary health care*. Stockholm, Sweden
- Yücel Z, Koç M, 2011. İlköğretim Öğrencilerinin Matematik Dersine Karşı Tutumlarının Başarı Düzeylerini Yordama Gücü ile Cinsiyet Arasındaki İlişki. *İlköğretim Online* 10(1): 133-143.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Education Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).